

House-of-cards composites of MWW monolayers and TiO₂ nanoparticles with (photo)catalytic activity

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ABSTRACT

The exfoliation of layered zeolites affording monolayer nanosheets in solution enables for the first time preparation of molecularly intimate composites of zeolites with other components like nanoparticles, other layers, etc. This ability is not possible with the conventional 3D and even solid 2D zeolite forms. It allows synthesizing composites with desired combination of functionalities and additional benefits like open accessible architectures. The present article illustrates this novel approach by reporting the preparation of catalysts comprising 2.5 nm thick monolayers of the zeolite MWW and TiO₂ nanoparticles with approximate diameter 4–8 nm. The chosen ratio is 1:1 w/w but it is readily adjustable to different values if desired. Two solutions of exfoliated zeolite MWW monolayers were used: as-made and after purification by dialysis. The composites precipitated upon mixing with TiO₂ nanoparticle solutions. TEM investigation confirmed random mixing of the components producing house-of-cards structures. The composites were additionally characterized by X-ray powder diffraction, nitrogen sorption and FTIR. The efficacy of the new approach was demonstrated through testing in two catalytic oxidation reactions, and both showed advantage over the equivalent physical mixture of the components. One of the test reactions, diphenyl sulfide oxidation by H₂O₂ revealed both catalytic (in the dark) and photocatalytic (with irradiation) activity. The hydroxylation of terephthalic acid occurred by radical oxidation. The presented approach can be applied to design desired systems, e.g., with other semiconductors to allow more precise control not only of the content in mixed phases but also of optical and electronic properties of these materials.

1. Introduction

Catalysis facilitates both the conceptualization and implementation of sustainable methodologies and processes [1,2]. Both zeolites and TiO₂ have a long history of enabling transition from environmentally deleterious procedures into more benign ones. TiO₂-based photocatalytic technology, started in 1972 with the discovery of water splitting [3], has been expanding since then and offer numerous examples of advantages in environmentally friendly projects [4]. Zeolites, on the other hand, are the key components in many industrial large-scale processes involving hydrocarbon conversions into petrochemicals, fuels, and lubricants [5, 6] as well as removal of harmful products like NO_x, SO_x and VOC among others [7–10].

Titanium dioxide was chosen as the active component in various processes due to its high chemical stability, low cost of production, and

lack of toxicity [11,12]. The specific surface area of TiO₂ is an important factor affecting its performance [13], however, its enhancement presents several challenges. One of most important ones include overcoming the potential for increased surface defects, including step edges, oxygen vacancies, linear defects, impurities, or increased potential for particle coalescence [14]. In photocatalytic applications, these defects can lead, among others, to fast recombination of electron-hole pairs, which significantly limits the photocatalytic activities of TiO₂ [15].

The high-surface small-size TiO₂ nanoparticles should be immobilized on the carrier to increase their stability [16]. Porous materials, such as clay, clay minerals or (alumino)silicates are very often proposed as the immobilizers, and demonstrated their ability to improve the dispersion, recoverability and catalytic performance of nano-TiO₂ [17]. It was also claimed that the acidity of the support may enhance photocatalytic activity for TiO₂ [18].

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Zeolite/TiO₂ composites based on diverse designs [19–22] are also intensely tested as catalysts and photocatalysts for operations such as the sustainable treatment of wastewater [23–26] or the degradation of gas-phase pollutants [27,28]. In an effective composite material, the active component, in this case titania nanoparticles, should be affixed to the support of nano-scale building blocks, such as nanosheets, which offer suitable void space based either on disorder or specific architecture of the constituent parts and easy access of substrate molecules.

In the case of zeolites, their micropores, limited to below ca. 1 nm, do not offer enough space to accommodate nanoparticles, therefore hierarchical, zeolite-based materials [29,30] are essential as matrices to be used as bifunctional catalysts. They combine the intrinsic high acidity and microporosity of classical zeolites with facilitated access and transport, enabled by the additional pore system acting as hosts for other materials, e.g., metal or metal oxides nanoparticles [31]. The hierarchy of the porosity in zeolites may be realized in many ways [32–36], one of the most desirable is the formation of disordered house-of-cards structures, build of extremely thin (down to the level of one unit cell thickness) zeolite nanosheets crystals with different spatial configurations, variable interlayer distances and minimized direct or parallel face-to-face contacts [37–43]. Few if any such architectures consisting of self-supporting nanosheets with edge-to-face contacts have been demonstrated in the literature. It is easy to imagine that such structures would be inherently unstable mechanically and instead re-stack face-to-face with more or less parallel packing of layers, driven by the high aspect ratio. Stabilization can be achieved by additional ‘spacers’ like nanoparticles to prevent direct planar layer contacts.

The exfoliated, fully crystalline zeolite monolayers in a homogeneous liquid may be exploited as ready-to-use pre-prepared dispersed building blocks allowing construction of hierarchical and nano-composite materials with other functional compounds, nanoparticles, and nanosheets [44–48]. Recently reported exfoliation of the zeolite MCM-56 [49] has afforded solutions of 2.5 nm thick MWW monolayers that allow combination with chosen components like nanoparticles. This new capability, unfeasible with the regular 3D zeolites or even unexfoliated 2D forms, is illustrated herein by the preparation of nano-composites constructed from MWW layers and TiO₂ nanoparticles with approximate 4–8 nm diameter.

MCM-56, together with MCM-22P and MCM-49 represent three principal forms of the zeolite MWW, which is characterized by two independent medium-size pore systems. MWW is known not only as an exceptional alkylation catalyst used commercially but also as the first framework recognized to grow as layers. MCM-56 consists of disordered stacks of single layers, MCM-22P consists of layers stacked in pseudo-ordered fashion, while MCM-49 crystallizes directly as conventional 3D crystals.

The oxidation of organic sulfides selected as a test reaction for these systems is one of the most important processes in organic chemistry, because the products (sulfoxides and sulfones) are essential byproducts for pharmacy and medicine, such as the production of antibacterial or antimalarial agents [50]. Similar activity is exhibited by TiO₂ [51]. The reaction itself is a representative of wide variety of photooxidation processes applied in the environmental remediation of toxic or harmful sulfur compounds especially using H₂O₂ as the oxidizer, due to its low environmental impact, nontoxicity, and high content of active oxygen. Recent reports show [52,53] that in the presence of hydrogen peroxide the oxidation of organic sulfides is catalyzed and photocatalyzed by P25 TiO₂, which is a mixture of anatase and rutile, with significantly higher conversion of phenyl sulfide by photocatalysis. In the present work this process was employed to show photocatalytic efficiency of the intimate MWW/TiO₂ composites prepared from exfoliated zeolite layers in comparison with physical mixtures.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis

MCM-56 was prepared as reported previously [49]. The dispersions of MWW monolayers were prepared by a two-step procedure by first stirring a sample of MCM-56 (0.5–1.0 g) with 10–15 g of 10 % tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (Merck, 40 wt. % in H₂O) for 2 h. After centrifugation of the slurry at 10,000 rpm (10 K rpm) to sediment all solids (30 min or longer) the supernatant was discarded, and the solid was stirred with 30 ml of water for overnight. The dispersion of monolayers was purified by repeated centrifugation at 10 K rpm, e.g., for 5 min, decanted, 5 min, decanted and finally for 20 min. The solution for subsequent use was pipetted from the top, approximate amount 25 g. Typical pH was near 12. The concentration of MWW nanosheets was determined by calcination of a weighted small amount of the solution (~2 g) at 540 °C for 6 h.

Optionally, the solution was further purified by dialysis inside a Spectra/Por tubing with 3500 Dalton cutoff immersed in 0.8–1 dm³ external water for overnight. The concentration of nanosheets was redetermined and usually stayed similar to the original solution.

The composites were synthesized by adding aliquots of commercial 5 % solution of TiO₂ nanoparticles with nominal diameter range 4–8 nm (5 % in water, anatase phase, HNO₃ stabilized, PL-TiO-5p-5 g, Plasma-Chem GmbH) to the above nanosheets with stirring. The product precipitated right away and was washed with water, dried and calcined at 540 °C for 6 h. Optionally the product was converted to a protonic form by exchange with NH₄NO₃, 2 times for 1 h, washed with water and calcined as needed.

The samples prepared for this investigation were 1:1 w/w composites of non-dialyzed and dialyzed MWW layers, marked 1:1 non-dial and 1:1 dial, respectively, and the mixture of MCM-56 with TiO₂ nanoparticles (1:1 mix). The last mixture was produced by mixing the parent solid MCM-56 with the solution of nanoparticles, followed by addition of 1 M ammonium hydroxide.

2.2. Characterization

Powder XRD patterns were collected using a Rigaku MiniFlex 600 diffractometer, equipped with a 2D Hypix400 MF detector, in the reflection mode, with CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm), 0.02° 2 θ step size (0.5° 2 θ per minute) usually starting from 1° 2 θ .

Zeta potentials were measured using Zetasizer NanoZS with MPT-02 Autotitrator and DEG0003 Degasser (Malvern).

Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms were measured on a Micromeritics 3Flex volumetric Surface Area Analyzer at -196 °C. All samples were outgassed prior to the measurements under turbomolecular vacuum pump using a Micromeritics Smart Vac Prep instrument; starting at an ambient temperature up to 110 °C with a heating rate 1 °C/min until the residual pressure of 13.3 Pa was achieved. After heating at 110 °C for 1 h, the temperature was increased to 250 °C (1 °C/min) and maintained for 8 h. Micropore and mesopore volumes were calculated from the isotherm desorption branch and BET area from a t-plot.

The structure of the MWW/TiO₂ composites was characterized by scanning transmission electron microscopy using a JEOL NEOARM 200F microscope, with accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Specimens were prepared by the direct deposition of powdered sample on a 300-mesh copper grid covered with a holey carbon film (EM Resolutions Ltd., United Kingdom).

The DR UV-Vis spectra were recorded using a Lambda 650S PerkinElmer spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 200–800 nm, with a 2 nm resolution. Samples were diluted with BaSO₄, the baseline spectrum of pure BaSO₄ was subtracted.

FTIR measurements were carried out using Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer, MTC detector, with spectral resolution 2 cm⁻¹. Calcined samples were exchanged with excess of 1 M ammonium nitrate solution

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of MWW/TiO₂ materials, calcined at 540 °C. Designations – dial and non-dial refer to MWW solutions dialyzed and non-dialyzed before mixing with TiO₂, mix – physical mixture of MCM-56 and TiO₂ nanoparticles. Rutile and anatase XRDs were generated by Mercury, using cif files from Crystallography Open Database, card entry 9,015,662 (rutile) and 1,010,942 (anatase). Apparent shift of MWW peak positions, especially the 100 reflection at the top, are attributed to instrument and packing effects rather than chemical or physical factors.

(>10:1 w/w), dried at 110 °C and pressed into self-supporting wafers with 2 cm diameter. They were activated in situ at 450 °C for 1 h at vacuum (10^{-3} mbar). Excess of CO (ca. 20 mbar pressure) was adsorbed at -100 °C, followed by desorption at increasing temperatures. Excess of pyridine vapor (ca 20 mbar equilibrium pressure) was adsorbed at 170 °C on the same sample, followed by desorption for 15 min at the adsorption temperature to ensure complete removal of weakly adsorbed species. The spectra were recalculated to a wafer mass equal 10 mg. Concentrations of Lewis (LAS) and Brønsted (BAS) acid sites were evaluated from the intensities of bands at 1454 cm^{-1} (LAS) and at 1545 cm^{-1} (BAS) using absorption coefficients determined earlier in our laboratory using external standards $\epsilon(\text{LAS}) = 0.165\text{ cm}^2/\mu\text{mol}$, and $\epsilon(\text{BAS}) = 0.044\text{ cm}^2/\mu\text{mol}$ [54].

2.3. (Photo)catalytic studies

The generation of hydroxyl radicals was examined in the reaction of terephthalic acid (1,4-benzendicarboxylic acid, TA) hydroxylation. MWW/TiO₂ samples (0.5 g) were suspended in 16 ml of the TA solution (Sigma Aldrich, 98 %; 0.003 M dissolved in 0.01 M NaOH, pH = 7.6) and irradiated with a xenon lamp (XBO-150, Instytut Fotonowy). To avoid TA excitation, a set of filters was used: 320 nm cut-off long pass filter and near infra-red and infra-red filters (10 cm optical path, 0.1 M CuSO₄). Samples with a volume of 1.5 cm³ were collected during irradiation, filtered through CME syringe filters with a 0.22 μm pore size, and then centrifuged to separate the solid photocatalyst. Hydroxyterephthalic acid (TAOH) concentration was calculated from emission spectra measurements ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 315\text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 425\text{ nm}$, PerkinElmer LS 55 Fluorescence Spectrometer).

Catalytic and photocatalytic oxidation of diphenyl sulfide (Ph₂S, 98 %, Sigma Aldrich) to diphenyl sulfoxide (Ph₂SO) and sulfone (Ph₂SO₂) in the presence of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30 %, Sigma Aldrich) was performed according to the procedure described elsewhere [53]. For both cases the reaction mixture consisted of 0.4 mmol of diphenyl sulfide in 10 ml of acetonitrile (99.9 %, Sigma Aldrich) and 0.1 mmol of bromobenzene (99.5 %, Sigma Aldrich) used as the internal standard. In a typical experiment, 5 mg of the sample (powder) was sonicated for 2 min in 10 ml of the reaction mixture, then 2 mmol of 30 % H₂O₂ was added (concentration in the suspension 0.5 g/dm³). Such prepared suspension was placed in a round quartz cuvette (5 cm diameter, 1 cm optical path) and irradiated in the same system as for the hydroxylation of TAOH. For the catalytic studies, the reaction tests were performed in the dark to avoid photoreaction. The reaction was monitored by HPLC

using the acetonitrile/water mixture (70/30 vol/vol) as the effluent. The samples were filtered using a 0.22 μm nylon membrane filter and analyzed by the PerkinElmer Flexar chromatograph equipped with the COL-Analytical C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm internal diameter and 5 μm pore size), column temperature 25 °C, UV detection at 254 nm.

Photocurrent measurements were conducted using a three-electrode setup with KNO₃ as an electrolyte (0.1 mol/dm³), purged with Ar for 15 minutes before and during the experiment. Ag/AgCl and platinum wire served as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. The working electrodes were prepared by evenly spreading photocatalyst suspended in water over a conductive support (ITO-coated transparent foil with resistance of 60 Ω/sq, Sigma Aldrich) and then dried at 60 °C. The working electrodes were irradiated from the backside through the ITO layer to minimize the influence of the film thickness. The potential and light were controlled throughout the experiment by the photoelectric spectrometer (Instytut Fotonowy). The Incident Photon to Current Efficiency (IPCE) values were automatically calculated from the registered photocurrent and incident light.

3. Results and discussion

Although there are over 15 distinct forms of the MWW framework with different layer arrangements, including seven obtained by direct synthesis [55], only the homogeneous solutions of exfoliated nanosheets that became available recently [45] enable intimate combination with nanoparticles such as TiO₂. Alternative approaches using solid layered zeolites as substrates are not as effective in ensuring complete (homogeneous) intermixing.

The process of dispersing 2D zeolites into monolayers in solution, e. g. approximately 2.5 nm thick nanosheets of MWW, is called exfoliation following the Glossary of Clay Science [56]. Delamination is a related term often used interchangeably but it is defined differently by the Glossary and commonly means layer disorganization of zeolite layers [44]. Finding suitable condition to directly exfoliate layered zeolites was challenging and required rigorous proving. The evidence of complete exfoliation was based on a combination of 6 characterization techniques [49]. They included: Atomic Force Microscopy (confirming single layers deposited from solution onto a support), in situ X-ray diffraction (proving single layers in solution), SAXS (showing complete loss of basal reflections for the layers below ca. 4 % TBAOH concentration), in-plane X-ray diffraction (provides planar lattice constants and XRD pattern matching MWW and its structure), TEM and ED to further confirm nature and structure of the layers. Additional evidence was provided by

Fig. 2. Representative STEM images of 1:1 non-dial MWW/TiO₂ sample and EDS elemental mapping.

re-stacking of the dispersed layers upon addition of a solution of surfactant, hexadecyltrimethylammonium chloride. The obtained product consisted of zeolite monolayers separated by surfactant bilayers with overall basal spacings around 5 nm (proved by powder XRD and TEM). Such structures cannot be assembled from multilayered particles if present in the solution. Furthermore, TEM images in this article show composites with predominantly single layers separated by titania nanoparticles. This also confirms that the layers were separated before mixing with nanoparticles, i.e., proved complete initial exfoliation.

The MWW layers/TiO₂ composites precipitated upon mixing solutions of exfoliated MWW layers (negatively charged) and commercial solutions of TiO₂ nanoparticles with approximately 4–8 nm diameter (positively charged). MWW nanosheets zeta potential was reported earlier as equal to -30 mV [57]. Zeta potential determined for TiO₂ was

equal to +0.33 mV. The as-synthesized solutions with MWW layers have approximate pH ~12 and were used both directly as well as after dialysis, which lowers the pH below 10. In earlier studies purification by dialysis was advantageous for catalytic activity of final MWW layers [46] so its effect was also examined as part of this work. As shown in detail below, the non-dialyzed solutions afforded more active composite oxidation catalysts. Phase composition of the precipitated products was examined by powder X-ray diffraction, shown in Fig. 1, which confirmed the presence of both MWW layers and TiO₂ as anatase. The MWW layers, even when disorganized, give the characteristic powder XRD patterns with relatively sharp finger-print intralayer peaks at 7.1, 14.2 (after calcination at 540 °C), 25 and 26° 2θ (Cu Kα radiation, λ = 0.154 nm used throughout) with Miller indices 100, 200, 220 and 310. A broad band between 8–10° 2θ, proves layer disorder contrasting the pattern for

Fig. 3. Representative STEM image of 1:1 non-dial MWW/TiO₂ sample(A) and SAED pattern (B).

Fig. 4. Selected house-of-card structure representations.

the 3D MWW framework with separated peaks at ca. 8 and 10° 2 θ . The XRD patterns in Fig. 1 indicate preservation of the MWW structure and reveal the presence of anatase showing peaks visible at 25.4 and 38° 2 θ . Noteworthy feature is the absence of a low angle reflection at 2° 2 θ and lower, which if present would indicate a sandwich-like pillared structure.

In the XRD patterns below 7° 2 θ the composite 1MWW:1TiO₂ non-dial and the physical mixture show a steep rise in the scattering intensity but without discernible peaks or shoulders that might indicate regular stacking domains. The 1MWW:1TiO₂ dial composite also has no low angle peaks between 1.5–2.5° 2 θ , however the XRD exhibits broad scattering with maxima at roughly 3.1 and 4.9° 2 θ (2.8 and 1.8 nm d-spacing; MWW layer thickness is 2.5 nm corresponding to 3.5° 2 θ). The origin of these peaks is obscure. One possibility is that these are non-Bragg reflections (not related to lattice planes) often exhibited by MWW materials due to very thin crystals [46]. Another possibility is that the first maximum with d-spacing 2.8 nm could be due to the presence of regions with stacked MWW layers separated by TiO₂ nanoparticles. TEM examination did not indicate the presence of such regions or their content is zero or very low. Although dialyzing seems unnecessary from the standpoint of textural properties and catalysis (vide infra) the different XRD features discussed above can justify further studies and attention.

Internal structure of the composites was revealed by TEM imaging, showing both layers and nanoparticles clearly visible and randomly interspersed (Fig. 2). The average size of nanoparticles remained practically unchanged, i.e., ~4–8 nm. Zeolite nanosheets are also preserved, frequently as monolayers although in some cases stacks of two or more layers also appear (Fig. 2b-d).

Considering the random architecture observed in the TEM (Fig. 3), the composites can be viewed as house-of-cards structures. In a mixture with multitude of layers their orientation can be recognized only for

Fig. 5. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms for reference MCM-56, its exfoliated derivative material (MCM-56 exfol) and MWW/TiO₂ samples. Isotherms are vertically shifted by 200 cm³/g for better data visualization.

those in a favorable nearly perpendicular orientation while the rest is difficult to identify and to determine orientation in space. Hence, it is justified to adopt a broad house-of-cards description for all disordered cases when no near-parallel stacking can be observed. There is also difficulty in proposing realistic graphical models. Fig. 4 illustrates selected models from the literature [58]. There may be a special example of a stable house-of-cards structure observed with intergrown MFI

Table 1

Textural parameters from low-temperature nitrogen adsorption and concentration of Brønsted (BAS) and Lewis (LAS) acid sites from pyridine adsorption, IR spectroscopy.

sample	surface area, m ² /g BET	pore volume, cm ³ /g		Ti content, %	acid sites concentration, μmol/g		
		micro	meso		BAS	LAS-Al	LAS-Ti
MCM-56 parent	514	0.087	0.04	0	669	148	0
MCM-56 exfol	566	0.108	0.08	0	598	180	0
1:1 mix	384	0.042	0.37	49.6	313	61	199
1:1 dial	412	0.048	0.38	50.1	272	25	118
1:1 non-dial	460	0.035	0.57	54.8	276	41	134

Fig. 6. Spectra of pyridine adsorbed on parent MCM-56 and MWW/TiO₂ samples at 170 °C. Spectra are vertically shifted for better data visualization, normalized to the same sample mass.

nano-sheets obtained bottom-up through synthesis [42]. It is not applicable to the post-synthesis top-down cases represented in this article.

The randomness of MWW layer orientations and spherical TiO₂ nanoparticles is particularly well visible in the image in Fig. 3 and the accompanying SAED. The former highlights the feature associated with and justifying the house-of-cards structure description. SAED on the right shows reflections due to MWW (closer to the center) and TiO₂, further away. Additionally, the image shows crystalline layers with various orientations (polycrystalline circles) and further away from the center one can also see bright spots from other randomly oriented TiO₂ nanoparticles (the same features are presented as insets to Fig. 2a and b).

The next important property of interest is porosity. Fig. 5 presents the corresponding nitrogen isotherms. The textural properties are summarized in Table 1. All isotherms belong to IUPAC type IV, with H2 hysteresis loops [59–61], which differ in significant details as discussed in the next paragraph. The composites BET surface areas of 384–460 m²/g are lower than for the pure MWW samples. This can be rationalized based on density of TiO₂, which is roughly twice that of MWW zeolites (~2 g/cm³). For the 50 % TiO₂ content this should reduce the apparent porosity by 25 % based on the weight basis. It is worth pointing out that the composites show higher BET area and mesopore volume than the physical mixture, especially the non-dialyzed one, which is also most active catalytically, as reported below. All three mixed MWW/TiO₂ samples exhibit reduced micropore volume between 0.035 and 0.048 cm³/g reflecting that (microporous) layers are present as only half of the

Fig. 7. IR spectra in the OH region recorded after activation at 450 °C.

sample.

The notable feature of the isotherms is change in the shape of the adsorption-desorption hysteresis, probably reflecting different nature of interlayer structure and/or spatial arrangement of the layers. The intimate composites show a distinct plateau in the desorption branch on the high-pressure side, which may be caused by cavity-like spaces with constrained entrances. In contrast, both pure MWW materials and the physical mixture of MCM-56 and TiO₂ nanoparticles show immediate falling off of the desorption branch from the high end-point pressure point, i.e., $p/p^0 = 1$.

The presence of TiO₂ nanoparticles, interspersed with layers, should not influence the properties and concentration of the acid sites located in the micropores. The entrances to the micropores and, therefore, the access to the acid sites is not blocked because after pyridine adsorption, the IR maxima characteristic of Si-OH-Al groups at 3628 cm⁻¹ disappear completely (all OH groups react with pyridine). The BAS concentration (Table 1) is nominally the highest for the physical mixture (313 μmol/g), while both dialyzed and non-dialyzed samples have slightly lower but similar concentrations of acid sites (ca. 270 μmol/g). In all cases, the concentrations of acid sites are lower than for pure MCM-56 (BAS 669 μmol/g, LAS 148 μmol/g), mainly due to dilution (roughly by half) of the zeolite content by TiO₂. The IR maximum at 1445 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 6) is characteristic of pyridine coordinatively bonded to TiO₂ [62]. In two samples: dialyzed and non-dialyzed additional pyridine band appeared, at 1422 cm⁻¹, close to the maximum characteristic of physisorbed pyridine (1405 cm⁻¹) but resistant to desorption at 170 °C. Such maximum was observed by Jia et al. [63] when pyridine was adsorbed on TiO₂ nanocrystalline film, and the authors claimed that it is characteristic for pyridine in very close contact with the TiO₂ surface. When absorption coefficient ϵ_{LAS} is used to roughly estimate the content of such Ti-species, their concentration is ca. 60 μmol/g in the non-dialyzed sample and ca. 30 μmol/g for the dialyzed one. It has to be stressed that such IR band is absent when pyridine is adsorbed on the MWW layers that are recovered from solution. Although the exact nature of such species is unknown, and the concentration is quite low, the presence of this band suggests that the materials, originating from exfoliated zeolite layers, are different than just physical mixture of TiO₂ nanoparticles with MWW crystals.

IR spectra in the OH region are presented in Fig. 7. The difference between the 1MWW:1TiO₂ physical mixture and the other two samples is clearly visible. The intensities of the Si-OH-Al maxima (3628 cm⁻¹) are practically the same for all samples (reflecting similar acidity). The intensity of the Al-OH maximum is the most intense for the physical

Fig. 8. IR spectra recorded after adsorption of excess CO at $-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (top spectra) and during progressive desorption at increasing temperatures. A – TiO_2 in three forms: P25 (mixture of anatase and rutile), pure anatase and pure rutile, B – 1MWW:1 TiO_2 physical mixture, C – 1MWW:1 TiO_2 dialyzed sample, D – 1MWW:1 TiO_2 non-dialyzed sample. The spectra of MMW/ TiO_2 are normalized to the same sample mass.

mixture and less intense for the material obtained via exfoliation, which suggests that during formation of composites some of the extraframework aluminum is removed. The main difference, however, is the intensity of IR maxima, characteristic of silanol groups. Two IR maxima are present for all samples – the higher wavenumber component (3750 cm^{-1}) is characteristic of terminal, isolated silanols, the lower wavenumber one (3743 cm^{-1}), for vicinal, hydrogen-bonded silanols [64]. The maximum characteristic of isolated silanols is much lower for the 1MWW:1 TiO_2 physical mixture, indicating their reduced population. This can result from interlayer condensation of the MWW nanosheets, which are never separated, contrary to those exfoliated and subsequently kept apart by the nanoparticles preventing silanol condensation.

The speciation of Ti species may be determined using CO as the probe molecule [65]. The IR maxima at the $2180\text{--}2190\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range (Fig. 8), present for all samples, are characteristic of CO species perpendicularly adsorbed on the surface of TiO_2 nanoparticles [66], most probably anatase 101 surface [67]. The shift towards lower wavenumbers during desorption is very often observed and explained by disappearance of the lateral interactions between adsorbed CO molecules with decreasing coverage [68].

It is very hard to determine origin of the maxima appearing around $2160\text{--}2165\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the literature the band at 2160 cm^{-1} is attributed to

CO adsorbed on the OH groups existing on TiO_2 nanoparticle surfaces [69,70], Ti centers of weak Lewis acid character located at 001 face of anatase [71,72] or CO adsorption on pentacoordinated Ti^{4+} bound to bi-coordinated O^{2-} on 111 rutile face [73]. When CO was adsorbed on pure anatase, an intense maximum at 2160 cm^{-1} appeared, therefore we assign this maximum to the presence of Ti centers on the anatase, which is consistent with the fact that anatase nanoparticles were used for the synthesis of MWW/ TiO_2 composites. The presence of a small amount of rutile phase is not excluded, due to phase conversion of anatase to rutile upon heating [74]. Among all three samples the intensities of these bands are lowest for the non-dialyzed one. The 2138 cm^{-1} band is due to physisorbed CO [65]. Another possibility is that the band at 2165 and especially 2157 cm^{-1} are due to CO sorption on residual sodium cations [65]. However, during pyridine sorption no bands of pyridine interacting with Na^+ was observed (1593 and 1442 cm^{-1}), therefore the latter possibility may be excluded. It can be concluded that in all samples there is roughly the same available surface of TiO_2 nanoparticles in the form of anatase, with differently exposed faces, additionally it is also possible that very small amount rutile is present and is also interacting with pyridine.

DR UV–Vis spectra of composites are presented in Fig. 9. They are similar for all three samples, with the main absorption band at 280 nm ,

Fig. 9. DR UV-Vis of TiO₂ (P25 - mixture of anatase and rutile), 1MWW:1TiO₂ physical mixture, 1MWW:1TiO₂ dialyzed sample, 1MWW:1TiO₂ non-dialyzed sample, MWW zeolite.

Scheme 1. Hydroxylation of 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic (terephthalic) acid by radical oxidation.

which is not much different from the spectrum of P25 TiO₂ (containing 75 % anatase). The observed peak widening at lower wavelength is due to the presence of the zeolite, as can be seen in Fig. 9. In this region zeolite has its own absorption.

Catalytic and photocatalytic properties of the MWW/TiO₂ samples were tested in two (photo)catalytic processes. The first one entailed analyzing the ability of materials to photogenerate hydroxyl radicals.

The chosen reaction was the conversion of terephthalic acid (TA).

The only product, photoluminescent hydroxyterephthalic acid (TAOH), is formed by the reaction of TA with HO• (Scheme 1). This reaction determines the activity of TiO₂ in various photocatalytic reactions, providing a broad view of the overall photocatalytic activity of these materials [75,76].

The efficiency of HO• generation was the highest for the non-dialyzed sample and the lowest for the physical mixture (Fig. 10). The enhanced photoactivity exhibited by the MWW/TiO₂ composites in comparison to the physical mixture MWW/TiO₂ highlights the beneficial impact of the house-of-cards type of structure on the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ combined with zeolite materials.

Catalytic and photocatalytic properties of MWW/TiO₂ samples were further tested in the oxidation of diphenyl sulfide (Ph₂S) to diphenyl sulfoxide (Ph₂SO) and subsequently to diphenyl sulfone (Ph₂SO₂), using H₂O₂ as the oxidant (Scheme 2). This reaction may proceed both in the dark, with MWW/TiO₂ acting as catalysts, and under irradiation, with MWW/TiO₂ acting as photocatalysts. Regardless of the conditions, Ph₂SO and Ph₂SO₂ were the only detected products of diphenyl sulfide oxidation. The results are summarized in Fig. 11, presenting conversion vs. time, time of reaching 50 % conversion (t₅₀) and selectivities. As a general rule, irradiation enhanced rate of the reaction but in the case of the dialyzed preparation the effect was weak in comparison to the other two, where it was quite pronounced. Little is known about the dialyzed vs. non-dialyzed systems so it is hard to even speculate what may cause the differences in their effect on properties and catalysis. The positive take home message is that the as-synthesized solutions of MWW layers can be used directly without purification by dialysis, which is an additional step and may have negative impact.

The above catalytic and photocatalytic reactions occur on the same active centers and both may occur simultaneously under irradiation. The catalytic oxidation involves only the activation of H₂O₂ at TiO₂ surface without any contribution of O₂; in the absence of H₂O₂, no products were reported for pure TiO₂ under the same experimental conditions [52,53]. The mechanism of photocatalytic reaction was recently published by Mikrut et al. [53]. The reactive oxygen species, such as HO• radical (formed by H₂O oxidation by holes and H₂O₂ reduction by electrons), O₂^{•-} radical (formed by H₂O₂ oxidation by holes and O₂ reduction by electrons), and finally H₂O₂, are acting at different steps of the four-stage reaction. Under light, Ph₂S is oxidized by HO• and the holes to Ph₂S^{•+}. In the second stage, Ph₂S^{•+} is oxidized by H₂O₂ or O₂^{•-} to Ph₂SO. In the third stage, the holes oxidize Ph₂SO to the Ph₂SO^{•+} radical and in the final stage, the latter is oxidized either by H₂O₂ or O₂^{•-} to

Fig. 10. The results of terephthalic acid (TA) hydroxylation by HO• radicals to TAOH. A – dependence of TAOH formation (in µmol/dm³) on time, B – TAOH production rate for MWW/TiO₂ samples.

Scheme 2. Diphenyl sulfide (Ph₂S) oxidation reaction by H₂O₂ in the presence of MWW/TiO₂ samples. The products are diphenyl sulfoxide (Ph₂SO) and diphenyl sulfone (Ph₂SO₂).

Fig. 11. Results of catalytic (in dark (dk), closed symbols) and photocatalytic (under irradiation (lt), open symbols) diphenyl sulfide (Ph₂S) oxidation by H₂O₂ in the presence of the MWW/TiO₂ samples. A – conversion of diphenyl sulfide (Ph₂S), B – t₅₀ values, i.e., time when 50 % of conversion is reached, C – selectivity to diphenyl sulfoxide (Ph₂SO), D – selectivity to diphenyl sulfone (Ph₂SO₂).

Ph₂SO₂. When the reaction is carried on the classic P25 titania, independently of the conditions (dark or light), the main observed product is sulfone, deeper oxidation is enhanced when the share of anatase is increased [52]. Obtaining a catalyst that is more selective towards either product is attractive due to its potential industrial applications. All obtained materials exhibit high selectivity towards diphenyl sulfone. The undialyzed sample is not only the most active, but also reaches 100 % selectivity to sulfone after 150 minutes of reaction, and the reaction is accelerated by irradiation.

The results of catalytic testing presented in Fig. 11 show advantage of producing intimate composites of MWW layers with TiO₂ nanoparticles over physical mixtures, validating the exfoliation route. Dialyzing the solutions of zeolites nanosheets before mixing with nanoparticles is detrimental and as made solutions should be used. This may be caused by lower pH of the former, which may be conducive to nanosheet

association and result in lower mesoporosity detected by nitrogen adsorption.

The activity of Ph₂S oxidation under irradiation follows the trend observed in TA hydroxylation (Fig. 10). In both cases (in dark and under light) Ph₂SO is readily oxidized to Ph₂SO₂, which is specific to oxygen-rich conditions. The irradiated non-dialyzed catalyst was again the most active and only slightly less active in the dark. The physical mixture benefited most from the irradiation but was still less active than non-dialyzed in the dark (compare t₅₀).

The IPCE measurements, reflecting the photocurrent generation efficiency, were conducted for the studied materials. The recorded IPCE maps as the function of wavelengths and potentials (Fig. 12) indicate that the presence of MWW does not alter the spectroscopic properties of the samples, i.e., photoelectrochemical activity occurs below 400 nm, consistent with pure TiO₂. The IPCE are relatively low for all samples,

Fig. 12. IPCE as a function of the photoelectrode potential (vs Ag/AgCl) and incident light wavelength recorded for photoelectrodes covered with (A) physical mixture, (B) non-dialyzed, (C) dialyzed MWW/TiO₂. The red and blue regions correspond to anodic and cathodic photocurrents, respectively, while white areas denote a zero net photocurrent.

Fig. 13. IPCE ($\lambda = 380$ nm) in the presence of electrodes made of dialyzed and non-dialyzed MWW/TiO₂ composites. The measurements were taken in an aqueous 0.1 M KNO₃ solution with or without hydrogen peroxide for 1000 mV (A) and -200 mV (B).

but this is due to the non-conductive nature of MWW, which hinders electrical contact with the conductive substrate. The MWW/TiO₂ composites exhibit higher IPCE than the physical mixture, aligning with the observed photocatalytic activity in TA hydroxylation and (photo)catalytic Ph₂S oxidation. Given the crucial role of photocatalytic activation of hydrogen peroxide in Ph₂S oxidation, additional IPCE measurements were conducted after H₂O₂ addition as the oxidizing agent (Fig. 13). The results show that, while dialyzed and non-dialyzed samples exhibit similar activities in the absence of H₂O₂, the presence of H₂O₂ significantly increases cathodic and anodic photocurrents, particularly for the non-dialyzed sample. These results are in line with the Ph₂S oxidation with H₂O₂ and confirm the advantage of the non-dialyzed catalyst over the dialyzed one.

4. Conclusions

Novel method of the preparation of bifunctional catalysts was presented, in which high-purity products can be obtained. This was enabled by the availability of zeolite MWW monolayers exfoliated into solution, which were combined with TiO₂ nanoparticles and isolated as intimately mixed solid catalysts. The zeolite nanosheet solution was used directly or further purified by dialysis. The obtained materials were active in selected test reactions, diphenyl sulfide oxidation by H₂O₂ and hydroxylation of terephthalic acid by radical oxidation. H₂O₂ could be a substrate in reaction catalyzed by anatase but in photocatalytic reaction it becomes a source of hydroxyl and superoxide radicals, enhancing (photo)catalytic activity of zeolite/TiO₂ composites. The composites

were compared to the physical mixture of the layered MWW precursor MCM-56 and TiO₂ nanoparticles (sample 1:1 mix). The sample obtained from non-dialyzed solutions of MWW layers showed the best performance in both catalytic tests, which may be related to its highest mesopore volume. The presented approach can be applied to other systems, especially semiconductors, to allow precise control of their content and properties, such as optical and electronic, in the composites with zeolites.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wiktor Dubiel: Resources, Investigation. **Marcin Kobielusz:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Krystian Mróz:** Resources, Investigation. **Michał Mazur:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Li Ang:** Investigation. **Lucjan Chmielarz:** Validation, Resources. **Wojciech Macyk:** Validation, Resources. **Wiesław J. Roth:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jiří Čejka:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Barbara Gil:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All data are available in Zenodo open archive under the link <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13903120>.

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